

Mechanisms of the Bridge Cleavage Reactions of Di- μ -hydroxo-, μ -Hydroxo- μ -oxo-, and Di- μ -oxo-bis{bis(*o*-phenanthroline)-chromium(III)} Complex Ions in Acid and Base Media

SHAMBHUNATH BISAI, ASHOKE KUMAR SINGH and BISWANATH CHAKRAVARTY*

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 26 November 1996, revised 2 June 1997, accepted 9 July 1997

Mechanistic studies on the bridge cleavage reactions of three double-bridged complexes, di- μ -hydroxo-, μ -hydroxo- μ -oxo-, and di- μ -oxo-bis{bis(*o*-phenanthroline)chromium(III)} complex ions have been made in acidic (57–75°) and in basic (47–60°) media. In acid medium, bridge cleavage reaction of all the complexes takes place after transformation to the dihydroxo form, both by acid-catalyzed and acid-free paths. In basic medium, all the complexes transform to the di-oxo form which undergoes bridge cleavage by base-independent path only. Bond cleavage processes are similar in both acidic and basic media.

It is interesting to note that cleavage of mono- and dihydroxo bridged dinuclear complexes of cobalt(III), rhodium(III) and iridium(III) are highly influenced by acid, while that of chromium(III) complexes are usually not¹. In acid cleavage reactions of chromium(III), it was observed that the reactions primarily proceed through the acid-free path, while the contribution by the acid-assisted path is negligibly small^{2,3}. However, acid cleavage reaction of one of the title complexes di- μ -hydroxo-bis{bis(*o*-phenanthroline)chromium(III)} investigated long ago was reported to proceed only via the acid catalysed path with no contribution from any acid-free path⁴. In the light of the latter observation, it has become necessary to reinvestigate the bridge cleavage reaction of the complex. Nevertheless, in order to have a thorough picture of these reactions, we have included two more complexes, μ -hydroxo- μ -oxo- and di- μ -oxo- complexes of chromium(III) in our study. Reactions of these complexes in basic medium (aqueous sodium hydroxide) have also been investigated to establish the mechanism of bridge cleavage in basic medium.

Results and Discussion

Reaction in nitric acid medium: The visible absorption spectra of all three complexes were found to be rather insensitive to ionic environment, being same within the range of experimental error in aqueous solution and also in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ sodium nitrate solution. Fig. 1 shows the spectral scanning of the di- μ -hydroxo complex species in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ nitric acid solution at 70°. In the course of a day or two the spectra resembles to that of the spectrum of *cis*-{Cr(*o*-phen)₂(H₂O)₂}³⁺ complex ion and thereafter no change occurs on prolonged keeping. Isosbestic point was retained at 507 nm. No other complex species could be identified in the reaction mixture by ion-exchange separation or by other means.

Reactions in sodium hydroxide medium: The visible absorption spectra of all the three complexes in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide solution at 55° are shown in Fig. 2. Spectral curves of all the complexes in strongly basic medium are exactly the same having absorption maximum

Fig. 1. Spectral scanning of di- μ -hydroxobis-bis(*o*-phen)chromium(III) nitrate in acid medium; [Complex] = 5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³; [I] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [HNO₃] = 0.3 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 70°: (i) 0 min, (ii) 30 min, (iii) 1 h, (iv) 4 h, (v) 24 h and (vi) spectra of [Cr(*o*-phen)₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₃.

at 452 nm. The mull spectra of di-oxo-bridged complex in arbitrary concentration unit is also shown in the figure. Similarity of spectral curves of all these complexes indicates that in strongly basic medium all complexes transform to the di-oxo form. Absorption values at all wavelengths decrease with time, and becomes nearly zero at all wavelengths after 2–3 days. No isosbestic points could be observed with any of the complexes. Chromium(III) ion and *o*-phenanthroline are identified in this solution by the usual procedure⁵. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture is passed through a cation exchange resin (Amberlite 120, 50 XW, 100–200 mesh) in K⁺-form after neutralization with KHCO₃ when both the reactant and the product complexes are absorbed on the

Fig. 2 Spectral scanning of di- μ -hydroxo complex in basic medium; [Complex] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$, [I] = 1.0 mol dm $^{-3}$, [NaOH] = 0.1 mol dm $^{-3}$, temp. = 55 $^{\circ}$: (i) 0 h, (ii) 2.5 h, (iii) 5 h, (iv) 24 h, (v) spectra of [Cr(*o*-phen) $_2$ (H $_2$ O) $_2$] $^{3+}$ and (vi) mull spectra of dioxo complex in arbitrary unit.

column. The resin bed on being eluted with a 0.1 mol dm $^{-3}$ sodium nitrate solution, the dinuclear species absorbed on the column comes out first leaving the product complex in the column. However, on being eluted with a four molar sodium nitrate solution, the product complex also passes which is identified as *cis*-Cr(*o*-phen) $_2$ (OH) $_2$ $^{6-}$.

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR BRIDGE CLEAVAGE REACTIONS IN AQUEOUS NITRIC ACID MEDIUM

[Complex] = 5×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$, [I] = 1.0 mol dm $^{-3}$		$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (sec $^{-1}$)					k_1	k_2
Complex	Temp $^{\circ}$ C	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	1.0	sec $^{-1}$	dm 3 mol $^{-1}$
μ (OH,OH)	57	3.46	5.30	6.68	9.41	11.82	1.8 \pm 0.2	7.0 \pm 0.1
	63	4.99	7.31	9.23	11.82	15.78	3.2 \pm 0.2	8.8 \pm 0.1
	70	6.39	7.99	9.33	13.75	17.21	5.2 \pm 0.3	12.0 \pm 0.1
	75	8.83	12.7	15.78	19.63	24.23	7.9 \pm 0.2	15.7 \pm 0.2
μ (OH,O)	70	7.83	9.14	13.65				
	μ (O,O)	70	8.13	9.62	13.85			
						k_1	k_2	
						ΔH^* (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	77 \pm 4	48 \pm 4
						ΔS^* (JK $^{-1}$ mol $^{-1}$)	-105 \pm 12	-178 \pm 14

Kinetics of acid cleavage reaction : The reactions are followed spectrophotometrically at the absorption maximum of the complexes at 540 nm. The rate constants are evaluated by Guggenheim's plot. Average deviation in rate constant values is found to be within $\pm 3\%$ of the determined value. The rate constant values of all the three complexes, which are average of 3-4 values from separate runs, are given in Table 1. The plots of k_{obs} values versus acid concentration for all these three complexes are linear having a positive slope and a positive intercept on rate axis. The rate constants for acid-dependent and acid-free paths of the complexes are obtained from the slopes and intercepts of these plots respectively. The values of these rate constants are also given in Table 1. Acid-dependence of k_{obs} values gives a rate law of the form,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{H}^+] \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are rate constants by the acid-free and acid-dependent paths. The reaction stoichiometry and reaction products of the dihydroxo-bridged dinuclear complex leads to the mechanistic steps as shown in Scheme 1.

(a) Acid-catalyzed path :

(b) Acid-free path :

Scheme 1

On the basis of the mechanism, the overall rate of bond cleavage of the complex ion is given by

$$\text{Rate} = k'[\text{II}] + k''[\text{I}] = k'K[\text{I}][\text{H}^+] + k''[\text{I}]$$

$$= k_1 [\text{Complex}] + k_2 [\text{Complex}][\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

where K is the equilibrium constant for the formation of the protonated species (II) and k' and k'' are rate constants for the slow rate-determining steps for the protonated and non-protonated forms of the complex species. In deducing the above equation it has been assumed that K is very small, so that $[\text{I}] \gg [\text{II}]$. However, the second bond breakage is a fast one giving the final product as the diaquo species. Equation (2) is similar in form to the empirical rate equation as proposed in equation (1).

Activation parameters of the acid cleavage reaction of the dihydroxo complex as evaluated from Eyring equation show that the enthalpy of the acid-catalyzed path (48 ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹) is similar to the bond cleavage reactions of other chromium(III) complexes, but that of the acid-free path is much higher than this value (77 ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹). Acid-catalysis reduces strain on the bridging bonds, which is responsible for the observed lower enthalpy values.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR BRIDGE CLEAVAGE REACTIONS IN AQUEOUS SODIUM HYDROXIDE SOLUTION

[Complex] = 1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, $I = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³

Complex	Temp. °C	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)				
		[NaOH]	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6
$\mu(\text{OH}, \text{OH})$	47	9.06	8.72	8.88	8.62	9.02
	55	10.73 ^a	10.11	10.24	10.17	10.47
	60	15.53	15.82	15.89	15.79	15.71
$\mu(\text{OH}, \text{O})$	47	8.77	8.75	8.81	8.72	8.75
$\mu(\text{O}, \text{O})$	47	8.93	8.89	8.92	8.79	8.82

^aAt 55°, varying the concentration of the complex in the region $(1-3) \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, the k_{obs} values remain almost constant, 10.74 ± 0.08 s⁻¹. For the complex, $\mu(\text{OH}, \text{OH})$: $\Delta H^\ddagger = 43 \pm 4$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = 45 \pm 6$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

Base-catalyzed bond cleavage reaction: This reaction is followed spectrophotometrically at the absorption maximum of the complexes in alkaline medium at 452 nm. In strongly basic medium, all the three complex species transform to one form, the dioxo-bridged form, as indicated by the spectra having maxima at 452 nm. Rate constant values are obtained by Guggenheim's plot. The rate constants thus obtained for the dihydroxo species at different temperatures (47–60°) and for the other two complexes at 47° are

Scheme 2

given in Table 2. These values are the average of 2–3 runs and are within $\pm 3\%$ of the reported value. Rate constant values, within the range of experimental error, do not change with change in base concentration. This is true for all the three species. In strongly basic medium, all the species transform to the dioxo form after giving up the proton from the bridging ligand to the medium. This leads to the rate equation in basic medium as

$$\frac{d[\text{Complex}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} \quad (3)$$

The dioxo complex undergoes spontaneous bridge cleavage reaction in aqueous solution by the slow rate-determining path as shown in Scheme 2.

Activation parameters as evaluated by Eyring's plot are also given in Table 2. Bond cleavage processes seem to be alike in both the cases. Cleavage of first bridge is of prime importance. The second bridge breaks up in a fast reaction step as a followup process. For the present series of complexes, bridge cleavage reactions in acid medium proceed both through acid catalysis as well as through acid-independent paths. In basic medium, bridge cleavage takes place by base-free path only. However, mechanisms of bridge cleavage in acidic as well as in basic media follow similar processes.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes: Di- μ -hydroxobis[bis(o-phenanthroline)chromium(III)] nitrate, μ -hydroxo- μ -oxobis[bis(o-phenanthroline)chromium(III)] nitrate and di- μ -oxobis[bis(o-phenanthroline)chromium(III)] nitrate: All the complexes were prepared according to literature method⁷. However, in order to have the complexes in nitrate forms, nitric acid and sodium nitrate were used in place of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate.

Solutions of nitric acid, sodium nitrate and sodium hydroxide (A.R. grade) were made in double-distilled water. Sodium nitrate was standardized by the ion-exchange salt-splitting method by passing through a cation exchange bed in the H⁺-form and titrating the corresponding acid in the effluent with standard sodium hydroxide solution. Ionic concentration was maintained with sodium nitrate. A Pye-Unicam spectrophotometer was used for monitoring the kinetics of reactions. Sample quenching technique was adopted for absorbance measurements at suitable time intervals⁸. The kinetics of bond cleavage reactions in nitric acid for all the complexes were followed at 530 nm and in sodium hydroxide medium at 452 nm, corresponding to the absorption maximum of the complex ions. All kinetic experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions, that is, by using a large excess of the reagent over the complex.

Determination of protonation constants: Protonation constants of the dihydroxo complex were determined by pH-titration technique at the experimental conditions at 25°. A solution containing requisite amounts of sodium nitrate and the complex was titrated with standard sodium

hydroxide solution and noting the pH after each addition of NaOH. The protonation constants K_1 and K_2 were obtained from the equation,

$$\frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma} [\text{H}^+]^2 = \frac{1-\gamma}{2-\gamma} [\text{H}^+] K_1 + K_1 K_2,$$

where, γ is the ratio of $[\text{Na}^+]$ ion to [Total complex] and $[\text{H}^+]$ the concentration of hydrogen ion at the experimental pH. From the slope and the intercept of the plot of $\frac{\gamma}{2-\gamma} [\text{H}^+]^2$ against $\frac{1-\gamma}{2-\gamma} [\text{H}^+]$, the protonation constants (log value) $\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ were obtained as 5.37 ± 0.01 and 6.85 ± 0.01 respectively.

References

1. K. KAAS and J. SPRINGBORG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 387.
2. F. GALS BOL, S. LARSEN, B. RASMUSSEN, and J. SPRINGBORG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 290.
3. S. LEONE, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 1865; M. R. GRACE and L. SPICIA, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 2389.
4. D. WOLCOTT and J. B. HUNT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 755.
5. I. M. KOLTHOP and E. B. SANDELL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., MacMillan, New York, 1952.
6. M. P. HANCOCK, J. JOSEPHSEN, and C. E. SCHAFFER, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1976, **30**, 79.
7. J. JOSEPHSEN and C. E. SCHAFFER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1970, **24**, 2929.
8. B. CHAKRAVARTY and S. ADHIKARI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 583.